

SECTION OF EARTH SCIENCES

EVOLUTION OF PACKAGING MATERIALS: TRANSITION FROM TRADITIONAL TO INNOVATIVE ECO-FRIENDLY SOLUTIONS

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Abstract

This article explores the evolution of packaging materials and the transition from traditional solutions like plastic and glass to more eco-friendly alternatives. It addresses the main environmental issues related to traditional materials, such as ocean pollution and growing waste. The paper also discusses promising innovative solutions, including biodegradable and compostable materials, mushroom-based packaging, and bioplastics. It emphasizes the importance of legislative initiatives aimed at encouraging the use of sustainable packaging solutions. In conclusion, key challenges faced by the industry are highlighted, such as the high cost of eco-friendly materials and the need for the development of recycling infrastructure.

Keywords: packaging materials, ecology, biodegradable materials, compostable packaging, packaging innovations, waste recycling.

Introduction

Packaging plays a crucial role in maintaining a product's quality and facilitating the transportation and storage of items. Nonetheless, the rising utilization of conventional materials such as plastic and glass has led to a variety of significant environmental issues. Microplastics, marine pollution, and growing landfills everywhere indicate the need for a radical change in approaches to packaging solutions.

With the growing concern for the environment, many companies, researchers, and politicians came to a common view that it is high time to switch to more sustainable solutions. Eco-friendly packaging materials not only reduce harmful emissions but also open up new opportunities for creating closed consumption cycles.

The article is intended to give an overview of the theoretical aspects of the development of packaging materials, assess problems with traditional solutions, consider modern approaches and the role of regulation in promoting them.

Main part. Environmental problems of traditional packaging materials

Traditional packaging materials, including plastic, metal, glass and paper, are widely used due to their low cost, availability and versatility. However, their widespread use has revealed significant environmental problems that threaten ecosystems and human health. Of greatest concern is plastic. Much of this waste ends up in landfills or in the environment, where it takes centuries to decompose, and only 9% of plastic is recycled (table 1).

Table 1.

Plastic pollution by country [1]

Country	Plastic Pollution MWI	Plastic pollution MWI level	Plastic pollution total plastic consumption in tons of plastic waste	Plastic pollution mismanaged waste 2023 (tons)	Plastic pollution per capita plastic consumption (kg capita year)	Plastic pollution microplastic released into waterways (tons)
United States	8,71	Very low	22,9M	1992144	69	254,667
China	17,41	Low	37,6M	6546264	26,7	517,699
Russia	97,82	Very high	3,2M	3094976	22	47,987
Japan	10,87	Very low	3,8M	413770	30,2	172,872
Germany	8,34	Very low	3,6M	297559	42,9	74,309
United Kingdom	12,31	Very low	2,1M	256610	31,1	59,546
France	5,08	Very low	2,7M	136239	39,7	60,757

The Mismanaged Waste Index, or MWI, is a measure that indicates how much more the amount of plastic waste generated exceeds the capacity for recycling such waste in a particular country. A high value of MWI means more plastic waste is not properly managed and, therefore, contributes to environmental pollution.

Plastics, particularly polyethylene and polypropylene, are non-biodegradable. It does not biodegrade

but rather breaks down into microplastics, which are minute particles found in both marine animals and human individuals. An estimated 0,5% of plastic waste finally makes its way into the ocean, causing an estimated 350 million tons of plastic waste [2]. Because of the nature of plastic itself, it tends to persist and accumulate over long periods, mostly on the sea bottom. It should also be noted that glass and metal are very difficult to work with. While more durable and having

greater potential for recycling, their manufacturing processes emit a lot of carbon and require a great deal of resources.

Although it is supposed to be 'green,' paper packaging is also starting to cause substantial problems in terms of environmental influence. Making paper requires wood cutting, which means reduction in ecosystems' ability to absorb carbon dioxide. The production of paper is also highly water-consuming and involves many kinds of chemical reagents, among them chlorine applied for bleaching, that pollute the water [3]. Waste management problems compound the issue. Most developing countries lack the infrastructure to recycle or correctly dispose of packaging materials safely. This, therefore, creates waste that reaches landfills-emitting methane, a greenhouse gas contributing to global warming.

Organizations using traditional materials are becoming more aware of these issues and strive to reduce their environmental footprint. For example, **Coca-Cola** aims to use 50% recycled plastic in its packaging by 2030, as part of the World Without Waste program [4]. At the same time, enterprises like **Unilever** do not stop trying to transit to 100% recyclable packaging and to

move into 100% eco-friendly goods by 2039 [5]. However, it cannot be said that such efforts in principle solve the problem.

New eco-friendly packaging solutions

At the same time, greater awareness of environmental impacts related to conventional packaging materials has placed significant interest in finding sustainable alternatives among both scientific research and industrial manufacturing. New materials have lately been made available that attempt to diminish the impacts of packaging on ecosystems and reduce carbon emissions.

One of the most promising solutions is biodegradable materials. These materials, unlike plastic, are decomposed by microorganisms into simple natural components, which reduces their decomposition time very considerably and minimizes pollution. Examples of such materials include packaging made of **starch**, **polylactic acid (PLA)**, and **mycelium**. **Ecovative Design**, for example, works on the production of packaging made out of mycelium – the vegetative parts of fungi – that can replace plastics with a sustainable material. Its main feature is that of biodegradability. It also offers itself to be cultivated as a resource, which doesn't require many energies or any huge amount of water (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Mushroom packaging process [6]

Moreover, compostable packaging materials are also very significant because they completely decompose in the conditions of composting and leave no harmful residues in nature. This is already practiced in the food industry where the packaging of foodstuff needs to be safe as well as easily recyclable.

Recent advances in bioengineering and nanotechnology further open up the prospects for new packaging solutions. The rise of biopolymers derived from natural sources, such as cellulose and chitosan, enables the manufacturing of materials with much improved mechanical properties, which could be used in place of traditional plastics without compromising on quality or durability for applications in food and pharmaceutical packaging.

Innovative, sustainable packaging solutions are responding to the call of ecological issues and the rising possibility of new opportunities for business sustainability. These materials do require investment in new

technologies and recycling infrastructure that might ultimately change the fundamental aspect of the global packaging economy. However, a big obstacle still remains at the stage of mass production and distribution.

Regulatory and political aspects

Besides the technological advance needed, shifting to sustainable packaging materials has to be significantly complemented by efforts in the legislative and policy domains. As a matter of fact, regulatory measures and political initiatives are highly required as motivation for the production and use of sustainable packaging, therefore creating an enabling environment for the reduction of environmental impacts associated with packaging materials.

This makes the European Green Deal at most one of many initiatives, world over, that target sustainability of the economy with high emphasis on the packaging industry. Another important regulatory framework affecting the packaging industry is the EU Single-Use

Plastics Directive adopted in 2021, which requires that, by then, plastic items such as straws, plates, and cutlery must be completely phased out, while on the other hand, there should be an increase in the use of recycled materials for packaging applications. Besides that, it calls for producers to minimize the packaging they use other than just ensuring recyclability.

National regulations also play an important role in stimulating the transition to sustainable packaging solutions. For instance, different states in the United States, such as California and New York, have already introduced certain legislation that limits single-use plastics and requires companies to invest in recycling and the use of sustainable materials [7]. In 2021, California enacted the «Reduce Plastic Waste Act», where it was specified that 75% of plastic packaging within the state would be recycled or re-used by 2032. This law also mandates the application of recycled materials in packaging, which will drive the development of recycling technologies and secondary materials production [8].

More and more, it is realized that global and local carbon taxes are an important mechanism impacting the packaging industry. The establishment of carbon tax targeting production linked to plastics and other materials that complicate recycling becomes an economic incentive for firms to deploy resources towards more sustainable options.

Concurrently, actions taken by large corporations go a long way in the modification of policy. The World Without Waste program initiated by Coca-Cola, as mentioned earlier, is just one example of this. This program deals with the recycling of packaging materials and utilization of recycled resources, hence showing the positive impacts of corporate social responsibility on the development of sustainable technologies. Similar programs promote governmental agencies and other industrial sectors to participate more actively in the legislative and regulatory matters related to the packaging industry and environmental safety.

Assessing current features and challenges

In light of rising global environmental issues, the heightened interest in eco-friendly packaging materials is driven by greater public awareness of ecological challenges along with developments in new technologies. Despite this positive trend, the shift to sustainable packaging alternatives poses several significant challenges that must be considered when analyzing existing trends.

One of the major constraints to extensive recycling programs is infrastructure deficits in recycling, mainly in developing countries. A lot of the plastic wastes that are collected for recycling are seldom processed due to contamination or lack of adequate technology to handle the recyclable materials.

The second trend to watch is the use of biodegradable and compostable materials. While biodegradable and compostable materials offer the potential to reduce the environmental impact of packaging, significant issues arise with large-scale production and distribution. The first and foremost problem arises when many of these materials decompose only under

certain conditions, which are mostly absent in conventional recycling environments. Compostable materials decompose at high temperatures in professional composting facilities. Otherwise, they can be very stable for long periods when buried in landfills or even in marine environments. More importantly, there is a high chance that the materials will not be disposed of properly and can reach the environment without decomposition.

Socio-economic constraints strongly affect the transition process. The expense of manufacturing sustainable packaging materials, like bioplastics and materials derived from plants, is frequently more than that of conventional plastics. This is particularly accurate for small and medium enterprises that struggle to compete with large corporations that have access to inexpensive conventional materials.

An even more important concern is whether such a facility, dedicated to the treatment and recycling of new materials, has to be built. Compared with traditional plastics, which already have a large-scale recycling infrastructure in place, new eco-friendly materials require new systems and involve much investment and time in recycling.

Conclusion

The transition from conventional packaging materials to the latest environmentally sustainable alternatives is a very critical step in combating global ecological problems. However, traditional packaging materials bear numerous benefits but cause great damage to the ecosystems that result in the pollution of marine environments, soil, and atmosphere. Such challenges associated with the biodegradability and recyclability of these substances demand the establishment of new technologies in biodegradable packaging and compostable materials.

Innovative developments in this area include mycelium-based packaging, bioplastics, and nanotechnology that can offer very effective solutions to drastically reduce the carbon footprint of packaging. However, the broad application of these alternatives faces challenges relating to high production costs, inadequate recycling infrastructure, and developing new standards for the recycling of environmentally friendly materials. These are further complemented by the regulatory frameworks and policy initiatives, such as EU directives and legislation within the United States, to drive innovation and corporate responsibility toward sustainable packaging alternatives. Put differently, the implication here is that in order for there to be an effective transition to sustainable packaging, a holistic strategy must be followed through technological progress, policy, and the creation of recycling systems.

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